

Photon, Poynting Vector and Constant Velocity Electron

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In (1), it is argued that the Maxwell's equations for a photon [in E and B (electric and magnetic fields)] may be written as one equation: $d/dt (E+iB) = \text{grad} \times (E+iB)$ which is a quantum mechanical equation (with a vector wavefunction $E+iB$) and is similar to Dirac's equation for an electron. It may be noted that for a photon, E and B are perpendicular to each other and to the velocity vector v . Thus, the Poynting vector points only in the direction of v .

For an electron moving at a constant velocity v , the Poynting vector does not only point in the direction of v . There is electromagnetic flux in other directions. If one considers an electron at rest with electric energy density of $.5 \epsilon_0 E^2$ which is part of the rest mass, this does not simply become $[.5 \epsilon_0 E^2] v$ (to leading order for small v because B is very small) as a momentum contribution. There is an E_x component in the direction of v (say the x direction) which contributes to electromagnetic energy density. All energy terms from B_y, B_z, E_x, E_y and E_z contribute as do all three flux components. Thus, the situation is very different from that of a photon. We try to examine these ideas in this note.

Maxwell's Equation for a Photon as Quantum Equations

In (1), it is argued that Maxwell's equations $dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E$ and $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ for a photon may be written as one "quantum mechanical" equation: $d/dt W = \text{grad} \times W$ where $W=E+iB$ is a vector wavefunction. It is argued this is similar to Dirac's equation and it is noted that both a photon and a charged particle at constant velocity satisfy:

$$p^2 + m^2 c^2 = E^2 \quad \text{where } E \text{ is energy and } p \text{ momentum} \quad ((1))$$

For a photon $m=0$.

It may be pointed out that for a photon E and B are perpendicular to the motion of the particle and so the Poynting vector is parallel to the velocity. Thus, all electromagnetic flow is along the velocity direction. In such a case:

$$d/dt U + \text{grad} \cdot S = 0 \quad \text{where } S \text{ is the Poynting vector and } U = \epsilon_0 E^2 + 1/\mu_0 B^2 \quad ((2))$$

In other words, the change in electromagnetic density in time is due to the flux moving in the direction of the velocity. This seems to be similar to a moving particle picture.

A charged particle moving at a constant velocity also has E and B fields, a Poynting vector S and electromagnetic energy density U , but the scenario is very different. There is an E_x i.e. a component of E parallel to the direction of motion and also S_x, S_y, S_z Poynting components suggesting electromagnetic flow in directions other than in the direction of motion i.e. x .

If one considers an electron at rest and takes $.5 e_0 E E / c c$ to be a contribution to rest mass, once the particle moves at constant v , one does not obtain a contribution to momentum (to first order because B is very small for a low velocity) of $.5e_0 E E / c c v$. $\text{Grad} \cdot \text{Poynting vector}$, as noted, must account for changes in electromagnetic energy density which include both $E_x E_x$ and $E_i E_i$ pieces where E_i is the component of E perpendicular to x . The flow of S_x (made of $E_i B_i$) is not strictly associated with only the change in electromagnetic energy of $E_i E_i$ and $B_i B_i$, but also of $E_x E_x$. This differs from the photon case and indicates that one may not simply consider electromagnetic energy as translating mass.

Moving Charged Particle (Constant v in x direction)

For a charged particle moving at a constant velocity (2):

$$\frac{d}{dt} U + \text{grad} \cdot S = E \cdot j \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } S = E \times B / \mu_0 \quad U = .5 (e_0 E E + 1/\mu_0 B B) \text{ and}$$

$$J = \delta(x-vt) v$$

The E and B fields may be obtained by considering A and ϕ (magnetic and electric potentials) for a particle at rest and performing a Lorentz transformation (boost) to find A and ϕ in the moving frame. Alternatively, one may use a covariant form of Maxwell's equations (as done in (2)) i.e.

$$\text{D'Alembertian} \cdot F = \mu_0 J \quad ((4))$$

The results are:

$$E_x = kq / [g g] (x-vt) / [R_1 R_1 R_1] \quad E_y = kq / [g g] y / [R_1 R_1 R_1] \quad E_z = kq z / [g g] z / [R_1 R_1 R_1] \quad ((5))$$

$$g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv}$$

$$\text{The vector } R_1 \text{ is } 1/g (g(x-ut) y, z) \text{ so } R_1 \cdot R_1 = \{ (x-ut)(x-ut), yy/gg, zz/gg \}$$

$$B = 1/c c \ v \times E \quad ((5))$$

v is in the x direction so only E_i the portion of E perpendicular to x contributes and $B_x = 0$.

Setting $c=1$

$$B \cdot B = vv E_i E_i \quad \text{so } U = (1+vv) .5e_0 (E_i E_i) + .5e_0 E_x E_x \quad ((6))$$

The Poynting vector is:

$$S = 1/\mu_0 \{ v (E_z E_z + E_y E_y) [i] - v E_y E_x [j] - v E_z E_x [k] \} \quad ((7))$$

$S_x = v/u_0 [E_z E_z + E_y E_y]$ This is double the “momentum” associated with $.5 \epsilon_0 [E_z E_z + E_y E_y]$ (for $v \rightarrow 0$). For a charged particle at rest, $E_x = E_y = E_z = E_a$ so electromagnetic energy density is $.5 \epsilon_0 3 E_a E_a$, but $S_x = \frac{2}{3} [.5 \epsilon_0 3 E_a E_a] / c v$. Thus, one does not have electromagnetic energy (or mass when divided by cc) act as a particle with momentum given by the mass multiplied by v .

Given that E_x is present, and there is flux in all directions, one does not have the photon scenario of E and B perpendicular to x .

For a charged particle moving at constant v , the terms of:

$$d/dt U + \text{grad} \cdot S = 0 \quad (\text{away from the current } j)$$

are:

$$.5 \epsilon_0 \{ 2 E_x dE_x/dt + (1+vv) [2 E_y dE_y/dt + 2 E_z dE_z/dt] \} - v d/dx [E_z E_z + E_y E_y] + v d/dy (E_y E_x) + v d/dz (E_z E_x) = 0 \quad (8)$$

if one chooses x, y, z off the x axis. There is only current j along the x axis.

One may note that: $d/dt E_y E_y = 2 E_y 1/[R_1 R_1]^{5/2} (-3/2) 2 (x-vt) (-v)$ by (where b is a constant such that $E_y = by/[R_1 R_1]^{3/2}$ $R_1 R_1 = (x-vt)(x-vt) + yy/gg + zz/gg$ with $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv}$)

[As a detail, the $zz+yy$ terms give a result proportional to: $v(x-vt)^3 (1-vv) / \text{derivative}$ Here derivative is $(-3)/\{(R_1 R_1)^{3/2} (R_1 R_1)^{5/2}\}$. The no derivative case is $1/\{(R_1 R_1)^{3/2} (R_1 R_1)^{3/2}\}$.

The xx terms yield: $-3v(x-vt)/[\text{no derivative}]$ and $(x-vt)(x-vt)(x-vt)^3/\text{derivative}$

With $R_1 * R_1 = (x-vt)(x-vt) + (1-vv)(yy+zz)$ the xx and $yy+zz$ terms with a derivative in the denominator combine to yield: $3 v(x-vt)/[\text{no derivative}]$ which cancels the $-3v(x-vt)/\text{no derivative}$ term yielding 0.)

Thus, even though there is a Poynting flux contribution in the x direction i.e. S_x , it takes all terms: $d/dx S_x + d/dy S_y + d/dz S_z$ together with $d/dt .5\{ (1+vv) (E_z E_z + E_y E_y) + E_x E_x \}$ in order to obtain 0. Thus, the $E_x E_x$ energy and all three flux directions are important, unlike in the photon case.

Conclusion

In the photon case, one may consider motion in the x direction with E and B being exclusively in a plane perpendicular to the x axis i.e the y-z plane. For a moving charged particle, there exist E_x, E_y and E_z . There is a Poynting flux in all three directions (not just the x direction as in the photon case). Thus, one must consider the full expression:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cdot 5\{ (1+vv) (E_z E_z + E_y E_y) + E_x E_x \} + dS_x/dx + dS_y/dy + dS_z/dz = 0$$

In other words, even though there is electromagnetic energy $\cdot 5\{ (1+vv) (E_z E_z + E_y E_y) + E_x E_x \}$, the momentum flux in the x direction is not electromagnetic energy/ (cc) times v. A more complicated process occurs with fluxes in the y and z directions as well.

Given that in (1), Maxwell's equations for a photon are said to be quantum mechanical equations with $W = \text{wavefunction} = E + iB$, one may see that for E and B fields of a charge moving at a constant velocity, matters are more complicated. We consider this problem because if E and B for a photon represent quantum mechanics, E and B for a moving charge should also be representative of quantum mechanics. For example, the magnetic potential is often described as being composed of virtual photons. Matters, however, are more complicated for the E and B fields than for the photon.

References

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